

Table 2. Morphoagronomic attributes (av of 3 yr) of upland rice genotypes at Jagdalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India.

Genotype		Days to 50% flowering	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Fertile grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)
R281 PP 31-1	Poorva/IR8608-298	82	109	71	302	19.0	60	86
RWR78-71-9	T3/T141//T3	77	104	76	351	18.2	56	86
JR80-4-6	DR42/Ratna	84	109	66	313	18.5	57	87
JR84-7-1-19	-	72	99	70	261	19.6	65	84
RNR1446	Tellahamsa/Rasi	80	106	81	311	18.8	62	90
Culture 1	AC540/Ratna	67	94	95	324	20.6	61	87
Poorva	Saket 4/JR 2-331	70	97	65	320	17.4	53	86
Annada	MTU15/Waikaku	80	106	71	300	20.4	82	91
Tulasi	Rasi/white gora	81	107	79	305	18.2	66	89
Rasi	TN1/CO 29	83	110	76	316	17.8	64	89
Aditya	M63-83/Cauvery	66	90	75	288	17.8	58	90
Tellahamsa	H12/TN1	81	107	80	279	18.5	66	90
Badoldhan (L)	-	78	104	120	217	22.1	99	93

Regression coefficients (b) ranged from -0.16 to 2.01 (Table 1). The variance due to deviation from regression (s^2d) was -6.59-8.75. The stability parameters of seven genotypes were not significant, indicating they are stable yielders across environments.

Rice varieties Aditya and Tellahamsa had b values close to unity (0.89 and 0.87),

indicating their high stable performance across the environments tested. These varieties yielded above average and have been released for upland cultivation around India. Varieties Annada, Tulasi, and Rasi show slightly above average grain yield (Table 1). These b values were significantly deviated from unity, indicating they were more responsive under favorable environments.

Stability for grain yield in rice appears to be imparted by the stability of most of the yield attributes (Table 2). Genotypes Aditya, Tellahamsa, RNR1446, R281 PP 31-1, and JR84-7-1-19 were stable yielders over time. They are recommended for upland cultivation in Bastar Plateau Zone and for use in breeding cultivars with yield potential and adaptability. ■

Variability, heritability, genetic advance, and genetic divergence in upland rice

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Attempts to improve rice cultivars grown in the upland ecosystem have been limited. Systematic evaluation of the genetic variability and divergence of the existing upland rice germplasm is, therefore, important.

We studied genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic advance, and genetic divergence of

39 upland rice genotypes. Most of them were early-maturing indigenous cultivars from Madhya Pradesh, India. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with three replications, during 1993 kharif (dry) season.

The significant mean sum of squares indicated the strong variability among the

Table 1. Genetic parameters of variation in upland rice. BHU, Varanasi, India. 1993.

Parameter	Traits											
	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Primary branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Secondary branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	100-grain weight (g)	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain length (mm)	Effective tillers m ⁻¹ row length (no.)	Grain yield m ⁻¹ row length (g)
Range: Minimum	66.3	87.3	62.4	4.7	6.6	1.6	0.6	15.3	37.6	6.2	36.7	17.5
Maximum	96.3	124.3	108.2	10.4	32.2	2.8	3.1	25.0	158.0	9.9	251.0	82.0
Genotypic variance	47.0	85.2	198.3	1.3	27.3	0.1	0.3	4.4	576.7	0.8	1066.5	198.0
Phenotypic variance	50.7	100.1	211.1	1.8	33.9	0.1	0.3	6.9	636.4	0.8	1518.1	469.6
Genotypic coefficient of variation	8.6	8.6	15.9	13.5	28.8	13.2	29.1	9.9	25.4	10.6	44.8	25.9
Phenotypic coefficient of variation	8.9	9.4	16.4	16.2	32.2	13.9	30.8	12.5	26.7	10.6	53.4	39.9
Heritability (%)	92.8	85.1	93.9	69.4	80.4	90.7	89.6	64.0	90.6	99.9	70.2	42.2
Genetic advance (% of mean)	17.1	16.4	31.8	23.2	53.2	25.9	53.9	16.4	49.8	21.9	77.3	35.6
CV (%)	2.4	3.6	4.0	9.0	14.3	4.2	9.9	7.5	8.2	0.4	29.1	30.3

Table 2. Genetic divergence^a in upland rice. BHU, Varanasi, India. 1993.

Cluster	Genotype ^b	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Primary branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Secondary branches panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	100-grain-weight (g)	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain length (mm)	Effective tillers m ⁻¹ row length (no.)	Grain yield m ⁻¹ row length (g)
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		
1	Ateya, Agnichar, Badaebutta, Badelwa Bademokado, Barangi, Barhi deshi, Bhadailli, Baril bhadainu, Lal bhadainu 1, Lal bhadainu 3, Bakki ^c	77.7 (15.9)	102.7 (25.2)	93.4 (32.4)	8.5 (19.1)	17.1 (50.1)	2.3 (61.9)	2.0 (43.2)	21.5 (23.8)	93.6 (29.9)	8.2 (44.1)	74.5	59.7
2	Badsahbhog 1, Bastaria Batasi, Bhatta khuji, IR8 mutant ^d Akashi ^e	83.0	108.1 (15.8)	83.3 (48.2)	8.1 (32.7)	17.5 (69.7)	2.2 (42.6)	1.8 (24.3)	20.0 (29.7)	95.5 (20.3)	7.6 (60.7)	72.6	43.9
3	Amakoyell, Alsengha, Bakhlasal, Barhasal, Barhi, Bayo	82.5	112.4	99.8 (14.7)	8.6 (27.5)	19.8 (24.8)	2.6 (89.7)	2.4 (71.0)	21.6 (39.1)	98.9 (55.3)	9.1 (28.3)	17.9	61.9
4	Anokhi, Wishnoo bhog Tulasif	83.3	104.3	94.7	7.7 (16.5)	17.3 (43.0)	2.1 (70.6)	1.5 (51.8)	20.7 (27.9)	80.7 (34.2)	8.4 (33.8)	64.8	52.6
5	Badwani 5, Badwani-22, Bhatta dhan	73.0	95.4	89.9	8.9	17.6	2.4	1.9	22.9	96.3	9.7	60.7	61.8
6	Baduri, Bala, Bhatta goyandi	83.5	113.8	86.1	8.4	25.3	1.8 (16.1)	1.8 (22.9)	21.5 (63.9)	114.4 (44.3)	6.4 (99.4)	57.7	32.6
7	Badsah bhog 2	77.0	105.0	65.6	7.1	22.1	1.9	1.7 (0.0)	17.7 (44.0)	112.0 (26.9)	7.0 (80.2)	73.0	50.4
8	Bagri	66.3	96.7	63.7	4.7	6.6	2.5	0.6 (0.0)	15.3 (34.8)	37.6 (47.7)	8.1 (47.7)	251.0	51.5
9	Aerramindo, Lal bhadainu 2	71.0	111.0	78.6	8.8	18.3	1.8	1.7	21.7	100.1 (18.5)	7.5 (60.4)	52.3	61.3
10	Badal phool, Annada ^f	88.2	123.0	63.7	8.4	16.2	2.1	1.6	20.1	78.5	9.2 (18.4)	57.3	36.8

^aFigures without parentheses are mean values of the traits. Figures in parentheses are intercluster divergence values. Bold figures in parentheses are intracluster divergence values. ^bUnless otherwise indicated, other genotypes are indigenous cultivars of Madhya Pradesh, India. ^cLocal variety of Varanasi. ^dEarly mutant of IR8 developed at BHU. ^eRecently designated variety. ^fNational check varieties.

genotypes for the traits studied. The considerable range of variation expressed for the traits indicated good scope for genetic improvement (Table 1). Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) was the highest for effective tillers m⁻¹ row length (44.8%) followed by panicle weight (29.1%), secondary branches panicle⁻¹ (28.8%), grain yield m⁻¹ row length (25.9%), and spikelets panicle⁻¹ (25.4%).

Broad-sense heritability estimates ranged from 42.2% for grain yield m⁻¹ row length to 99.9% for grain length. Effective tillers m⁻¹ row length, panicle weight, secondary branches panicle⁻¹, and spikelets panicle⁻¹ showed high GCV along with high heritability, indicating effectiveness of selection based on these traits. Even though

days to 50% flowering (92.8%), days to maturity (85.1%), plant height (93.9%), 100-grain weight (90.7%), and grain length (99.9%) had high heritability, they had low GCV.

Genetic advance as a percentage of mean was highest for effective tillers m⁻¹ row length (77.3%) followed by panicle weight (53.9%), secondary branches panicle⁻¹ (53.2%), and spikelets panicle⁻¹ (49.8%). Along with high levels of genetic advance, these traits also showed high GCV and should be considered when selecting to achieve high genetic gain.

Genetic divergence was estimated using D2 analysis. Ten distinct clusters were obtained following Tocher's method of clustering (Table 2). Mean values for the

traits in each cluster and inter- and intra-cluster distances were determined. Genotypes from the following clusters may be selected for use as parents in a hybridization program: cluster 8 for earliness; clusters 8 and 10 for dwarfness; cluster 6 for secondary branches panicle⁻¹; cluster 3 for panicle weight; clusters 6 and 7 for spikelets panicle⁻¹; and cluster 8 for effective tillers m⁻¹ row length. The highest genetic divergence was observed between clusters 5 and 6, followed by clusters 5 and 8, and clusters 3 and 6. This suggests that the genotypes belonging to these cluster pairs would produce wide spectra of variation in segregating generations following hybridization. ■